

ELECTRON MICROSCOPY ANALYSIS OF SQUEEZE CAST $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}\text{w}/\text{AZ91D}$ COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Aluminum borate ($\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$) whisker reinforced AZ91D composites fabricated by squeeze casting process have good mechanical properties at high temperature and aging effects. In as-cast composites, MgAl_2O_4 layer is produced at the interface between $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ and Mg matrix with a uniform thickness of 20-30 nm. There are some preferred orientations at $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}/\text{MgAl}_2\text{O}_4$ and $\text{MgAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Mg}$ interfaces. This uniform MgAl_2O_4 layer prevents the direct reaction between the whisker and Mg matrix during heat-treatment under 700 °C. For T6 treatment, the precipitates were distributed uniformly in the matrix. Consequently, the whiskers were scarcely damaged, so that the degradation of high temperature properties is very little.

KEYWORDS: Electron microscopy, Aluminum borate whisker, Magnesium alloy, Interfacial reaction, Heat stability, Squeeze casting, Mechanical properties, Mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

Aluminum borate ($\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$) whisker has been of great interest as the reinforcement in metal matrix composites because of its good mechanical properties and high cost performance. $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker reinforced Al alloy matrix composites have a considerable potential for providing lightweight components exhibiting high specific strength, good elasticity, low thermal expansion and high temperature property [1]. Some composites are used in the automobile engine components. But their mechanical properties degrade by heat treatment because of the interfacial reaction between the whisker and matrix. The reaction mechanisms between the whisker and many Al alloy matrices have been analyzed and the relationship between the microstructure and mechanical properties has been discussed [2]. Recently, Mg based alloy and composites are widely noticed as lightweight structural material instead of Al alloys and composites. Many study on Mg based composites are related to SiC reinforcement [3-5]. But these composites are not suited to practical use, because of the high hardness and high cost reasons of SiC particles and whiskers. Recently, it is investigated $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker is good for the reinforcement of Mg alloys, and these composites have a the good mechanical properties [6,7]. But the reason why it shows good mechanical properties is unknown. In this study, the interaction between the mechanical properties and the fabrication condition was investigated by the microstructure observation using by electron microscope. So that the mechanical properties and heat stability of the composite were estimated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

$\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker (ALBOLEX type M-12, Shikoku Chemicals Co.) and AZ91D (Mg-9%Al-1%Zn) alloy were employed for the reinforcement and matrix. As-received whisker is a needle-like crystal and its surface is quite clear and smooth. The whisker is 10-30 μm in length and 0.5-1.0 μm in diameter. The composites were fabricated by a squeeze casting process at a

perform pre-heated temperature of 700 °C, a metal mold temperature of 200 °C and a molten temperature of 800 °C. A pressure of 50 MPa was applied for 60 s during squeeze casting. The volume fraction of the whiskers in the composite is about 25 %. In order to investigate the heat stability and the aging effect, some composites were heat-treated at 700 °C for 1 hr and T6 treated at 177 °C for 0-64 hr, respectively. Microstructure was analyzed using by scanning electron microscope (HITACHI/S800) and transmission electron microscope (JEOL/JEM-4000EX and TOPCON/ 002B).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the bending strength of the composites heat-treated at different temperatures. The strength of as-cast composites is about 570MPa, which is improved drastically compared with the monolithic AZ91D alloy. The strength of heat-treated composites at 500 °C is highest in all heat-treated temperatures, which is stable as compared with Mg contained Al matrix composites. The strength decreases constantly as increasing heat-treated temperature above 500°C. On the other hand, the strength of the T6 treated composites for 16 hr is almost equal to that of the as-cast composites.

Figure 1: Bending strength of Al18B4O33/AZ91D composites heat-treated for 1 hr at different temperatures and T6 treated.

Figure 2: Vickers hardness of Al18B4O33/AZ91D composites. (a) Effect of heat treatment for 1 hr at different temperatures. (b) Effect of T6 treatment.

Figure 2 (a) shows Vickers hardness of the composites and the monolithic AZ91D alloy heat-treated in different temperatures for 1 hr. The hardness of the as-cast composites is about 165 (Hv), which is improved compared with 60 (Hv) of the as-cast monolithic AZ91D. As increasing heat-treatment temperature, the hardness of both materials increases with the same behavior. The hardness of the composites at 800°C is 260 MPa. It seems that this high hardness at high temperature is mainly caused by the precipitation and growth of Al₁₂Mg₁₇ intermetallic compounds and the reaction products from the whisker and matrix. Figure 2 (b) shows the aging effect for Vickers hardness. Hardness of the as-cast composite and the monolithic AZ91D are 165 (Hv) and 65 (Hv), respectively. By the solution heat treatments, hardness decrease to 160 (Hv) and 60 (Hv), respectively. Hardness increases constantly as increasing T6 aging time till 64 hr, respectively. The aging behavior of the composites is very similar to that of the monolithic AZ91D alloy. It shows that the whisker dose not influence the precipitation mechanism of Al₁₂Mg₁₇ in matrix.

Figure 3: SEM images of extracted whisker from Al₁₈B₄O₃₃/ AZ91D composites. (a) as-cast, (b) heat-treated at 700°C for 1hr.

Figure 4: TEM images of as-cast Al₁₈B₄O₃₃/ AZ91D composites. Figure (b) is enlargement of figure (a).

Figure 3 shows the extracted whisker from the composites. Figure 3 (a) is the as-cast composites. The whisker surfaces are very clear and smooth, which is the same as the as-received whiskers. The whiskers seem to have no damage by squeeze casting. Figure 3 (b) is the extracted whisker from the heat-treated composites at 700°C for 1 hr. The whisker surfaces become to roughen with small irregularities. This is caused by the reaction between the whisker and matrix. There are the reaction products 'MgAl₂O₄ with spinel structure' on the whisker surface. The reaction products are produced by the following reaction formula.

In Mg contained Al matrix alloy composite, Al₁₈B₄O₃₃ react vigorously with Mg to form island like MgAl₂O₄ on the whiskers. The whiskers become fine and short partially, so that the whisker strength decreased drastically by this reaction [6]. In this case, the whisker is not damaged because of low reactivity.

Figure 4 shows the micrographs around the interface between the whisker and matrix in as-cast composite. There is the reaction layer between Al₁₈B₄O₃₃ and Mg matrix with a uniform thickness of 20-30 nm, which forms triangle on the whisker microscopically as shown in fig. 1 (b). The whisker is covered with the reaction layer completely.

Figure 5 is the interfacial structure between $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ and MgAl_2O_4 in as-cast composites. The observation direction is parallel to $[110]$ in $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$. (120) plane in $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ is parallel to (100) plane in MgAl_2O_4 . It shows that MgAl_2O_4 layer grows epitaxially on $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker. $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}/\text{MgAl}_2\text{O}_4$ interface has a preferred orientation. It seems this interface has good bonding strength.

Figure 5: HREM image of the interface between $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ and MgAl_2O_4 in $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}/\text{AZ91D}$ composites.

Figure 6 is the interfacial structure between MgAl_2O_4 and Mg in as-cast composites. (111) plane in MgAl_2O_4 interface is almost parallel to (102) and (110) planes in Mg, whose interface seems to have a parallel orientation. $\text{MgAl}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Mg}$ interface has a good bonding strength. In case of Mg contained Al alloy matrix composites, the good coherence of the reaction product in matrix is usually not observed, and crack tend to propagate along this interface. This interfacial strength generally plays a part in the composite strength [6]. But in this case, it is

Figure 6: HREM image of the interface between MgAl_2O_4 and Mg matrix in $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}/\text{AZ91D}$ composites.

considered that the interfacial strength does not strongly affect to the composite strength.

Figure 7 shows the interfacial structure between the whisker and matrix in the composites heat-treated at $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1hr. The whisker is covered completely by the reaction layer. Although the reaction layer grows largely in here and there, the reaction layers scarcely grow on the average. The uniform reaction layer fabricated during squeeze casting process prevents the direct reaction of the whisker and the matrix, so that the composite is stable for heat treatment compared with Al alloy matrix composites. In case of Al matrix composites, the whisker and matrix react directly and lead to the whisker damage [6]. The heat stability of AZ91D matrix composite is superior than that of Al alloy matrix composites.

Figure 8 shows the microstructure of the heat-treated composite by T6 treatment. The many fine black-white contrasts in matrix are caused by the precipitates. Many precipitates distribute uniformly in matrix in the composites. It seems that the whisker has no influence on the precipitation. On the other hand, there are many cracks at the whisker/ matrix interface and in the whiskers. It seems that cracks are introduced by the strain caused by the precipitation. The degradation of the strength of the composites is not observed, but these cracks could be the cause of the low strength.

Figure 7: TEM image of heat-treated Al₁₈B₄O₃₃/AZ91D composites at 700 °C for 1 hr.

Figure 8: TEM image of T6 treated Al₁₈B₄O₃₃/AZ91D composites.

CONCLUSIONS

Al₁₈B₄O₃₃ whiskers reinforced AZ91D matrix composites were fabricated by squeeze casting process, and observed the interfacial structure by SEM and TEM in order to investigate the relationship between the mechanical properties and the interfacial structure. These results can be summarized as follows:

- 1) The bending strength of the composites is improved by heat-treatment at 500 °C for 1hr. As increasing heat treatment temperature and T6 treatment time, Vickers hardness increased constantly. These tendencies are same as the monolithic AZ91D.
- 2) MgAl₂O₄ layer with a uniform thickness of 20-30 nm covered the whiskers by squeeze casting. This uniform MgAl₂O₄ layer prevents the direct reaction between Al₁₈B₄O₃₃ and Mg during heat-treatment and T6 treatment. The whiskers are almost not damaged at high temperature. The Al₁₈B₄O₃₃/ MgAl₂O₄ and MgAl₂O₄/ Mg interfaces have preferred orientations.
- 3) The good mechanical properties at high temperature are caused by the low reactivity at the interface between the whisker and matrix.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by a Grant-in- Aid (No.09650749) from the Ministry of Education, Science, Sports and Culture of Japan, and performed under the inter-university cooperative research program of Institute for Materials Research, Tohoku University.

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